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COVER ART – The cover art was painted by Jason Poole and depicts a school of Mosasaurs.

A LARGE LONGIROSTRINE CROCODYLIAN FROM THE PALEOCENE VINCENTOWN FORMATION IN BURLINGTON COUNTY, NEW JERSEY AND ASSOCIATED INVERTEBRATE FAUNA.

SADOWSKI, Henry J., CALLAHAN, Wayne R., EHRET, Dana J., CONTI, Lawrence G. SHANKLE, William J and PARRIS, Dave C., New Jersey State Museum, PO Box 530, Trenton, New Jersey 08825-0530

ABSTRACT -The Late Paleocene Vincentown Formation in New Jersey has a fossil fauna rich in invertebrates, especially bryozoans, echinoids and foraminifers. Vertebrate fossils, from the Vincentown Formation, include chondrichthyan teeth, bird bones and isolated snake remains. Additionally, the remains of several longirostrine crocodylians have been reported, including '*Crocodylus clavirostris* Morton 1845, *Thoracosaurus neocesariensis* (de Kay 1842) and *Eosuchus minor* (Marsh 1870). Here we report on the recovery, by the New Jersey State Museum in 2016, of a nearly complete mandible and associated material of a very large longirostrine crocodylian (NJSM 24294) from the upper part of the Vincentown Formation of Burlington County, New Jersey. This is an on-going project and this report is meant as a status report. A complete description of the elements and phylogenetic analysis will be published at a future date.

INTRODUCTION

The material discussed here was discovered by Anthony Lawrence, in February 2016, while he was hiking near his home along Sharps Run, a small stream in Medford Township, Burlington County, New Jersey. The unusually warm temperatures during that month had brought heavy rainfall which had altered the usual visible ground surface. He noticed the tops of two black teeth, each about 6 cm in length piercing through the trail surface. Light digging by Mr. Lawrence revealed that the teeth were imbedded within a partial jaw fragment (**Figure 1**). He also noted a number of bones that were coated with yellow-orange matrix. He gathered his finds and sent pictures to various area websites seeking information. When his inquiry was brought to the attention of the staff of the New Jersey State Museum, David Parris, the Curator of Natural History, recognized the discovery as the mandibular portions of a crocodylian and the probable lithologic unit as the Vincentown Formation. Mr. Parris and various research associates visited the site with Mr. Lawrence and discussed the discovery, including the necessity of contacting the property owner.

Mr. Lawrence relinquished the fossils to the care of the New Jersey State Museum, and efforts began to gain permission for a proper scientific excavation.

The Medford Mill Homeowners Association, owner of the property, generously gave permission for excavation of the site, including donation of all fossils found there. New Jersey State Museum Research Associates, all of whom are volunteers, proceeded with the field recovery and, with assistance from Assistant Curator Dana Ehret, laboratory preparation of the crocodylian fossil and all associated taxa. This current report is an update to the preliminary announcement of this discovery by Sadowski et al., (2017) and the phylogenetic analyses of late Paleocene crocodylians of the Vincentown and Aquia Formations of the East Coast by Morgan et al., (2018). Work on the preparation, measurements and photography of the specimen is on-going.

METHODS

The site was collected by salvage prospecting, screening of matrix and manual picking up of specimens. Laboratory preparation was primarily by pin vise and dental tools, with some use of a

Paleo Tools Micro jack pneumatic air scribe. In some cases, matrix surrounding specimens was softened by soaking in water and/or weak acetic acid (under 10%) prior to manual preparation. All preparation was done in the Paleontology Laboratory at the New Jersey State Museum (**Figure 2**).

Institutional abbreviations—ANSP, Academy of Natural Sciences of Drexel University, Philadelphia, Pa; NJSM, New Jersey State Museum, Trenton, NJ.

GEOLOGIC SETTING

NJSM 29294 was recovered from the upper portion of the Late Paleocene (Selandian /Thanetian) Vincentown Formation. Gallagher (1993) describes this facies as a “yellowish gray clayey moderately to poorly sorted thin-to thick-bedded calcareous quartz sand to calcarenite.” Canu and Bassler (1933) described 85 species of bryozoans from this horizon with *Coscinopleura digitata* (Morton) being particularly abundant. Also recovered from this limesand facies are serpulid worms, a gorgonian, coral, bivalves, gastropods, rare brachiopods, crustaceans, a crinoid and several species of echinoid (Gallagher, 1984). In addition, foraminifera are abundant. Vertebrate fossils, other than chondrichthyan teeth, are uncommon in the Vincentown Formation. Gallagher (1984) reported bird bones and some fossil snake remains. The remains of several crocodylian taxa have been reported from the formation and these will be considered in the discussion portion of this paper. It should be noted that the Medford locality is approximately 7.5 kilometers southwest of the type locality for the Vincentown Formation along the South Branch of Rancocas Creek in Vincentown, New Jersey.

SYSTEMATIC PALEONTOLOGY

CROCODYLIFORMES, Hay, 1930

EUSUCHIA Huxley, 1875

CROCODYLIA Gmelin, 1789

GAVIALOIDEA Hay, 1930

‘*Crocodylius*’ *clavirostris* Morton 1844

REFERRED MATERIAL (Figure 3A)—Mandible, NJSM 24294, nearly complete left dentary with most teeth intact, 18 alveoli about evenly spaced with the exception of alveoli numbers 9 and 10 which are very closely spaced; the entire left splenial, beginning at approximately the 8th alveolus and extending posteriorly to approximately 10 cm from the 18th alveolus. Anterior portion of the right dentary including the 8th through the 16th alveoli; dorsal portions of the left angular and surangular; complete right articular with glenoid fossa and retroarticular process; additional fragments of the right angular and surangular and several additional, isolated teeth. The anterior portion of the mandible is fully articulated along the symphysis from its tip to the symphyseal divergence of the mandibular rami which occurs at approximately the 14th alveoli. Based on the nearly complete anterior portion of the left mandible and the posterior right mandible the estimated total length of mandible is 100 cm.

Post cranial material includes a complete dorsal vertebra possibly D9 or D10 (**Figure 3B**) and, at least, 6 whole and 3 partial osteoderms (**Figure 3C**). In addition, there are a number of bone fragments still in the process of preparation and identification.

Figure 1: NJSM 24294, Portion of mandible before preparation.

Figure 2: David C. Parris, Curator of Natural History (left) and Dana J. Ehret Assistant Curator of Natural History (right) line up mandibular sections of NJSM 24294 in the Paleontology Laboratory at the New Jersey State Museum.

Figure 3: NJSM 24294 major recovered elements: A. mandible; B. dorsal vertebra; C, osteoderm. Abbreviations: an, angular; art, articular; d, dentary; sa, surangular; sp, splenial; sym, mandibular symphysis; rap, retroarticular process. Scale as shown.

DISCUSSION

NJSM 24294 represents a very large gavialoid crocodylian. It was initially considered as belonging to the taxon *Thoracosaurus* which is well known in New Jersey (as *T. neocesariensis*) from the Late Cretaceous Navesink and New Egypt formations, and Early Paleocene (Danian) Hornerstown Formations. Crocodylians remains previously reported from the Vincentown Formation in New Jersey, and the equivalent Aquia Formation of Maryland and Virginia, include ‘*Crocodylus*’ *clavirostris* and *Eosuchus minor* (Brochu 2006; Morgan et al., 2018). *E. minor*, known from a fairly complete specimen NJSM 15437, from the Vincentown Formation in New Jersey and from more complete specimens from the Aquia Formation of Maryland and Virginia, has been “restricted to fossils of what appear to be a relatively small longirostrine crocodylian with a skull less than 50 cm length” (Brochu 2006).

Remains of a larger longirostrine crocodylian, ‘*Crocodylus*’ *clavirostris* (Morton 1844), was

originally “based on a partial skull from the New Jersey greensands” (Brochu 2006). The partial skull, ANSP 10079, was described as coming from “New Jersey, Upper Paleocene/Lower Eocene”. Carpenter (1983) considered ‘*C. clavirostris*’ to be a junior synonym of *T. neocesariensis* but Brochu (2006) noted “differences that separate the Late Paleocene” *C. clavirostris* “from its older relatives.” It is likely that *Thoracosaurus* should be restricted to crocodylians from the Late Cretaceous and Early Paleocene.

More recently Morgan et al. (2018), working with additional material from the Aquia and Vincetown formations, have assigned a number of skull and lower jaw material (including NJSM 24294) to ‘*Crocodylus*’ *clavirostris* based on phylogenetic analysis They place *C. clavirostris* as a “gavialoid basal to the *Eosuchus* clade” and estimate the total body length of the largest specimens to have been 8.25 meters. This work is on-going with histological studies planned in the near future. The expectation is that the species *clavirostris* will receive a new generic name.

ASSOCIATED FAUNA

Along with the skeletal remains of NJSM 24294 a large number of associated fossil taxa were recovered during the recovery and preparation of the specimen. These are typical of the fauna from the upper Vincentown Formation as reported by Canu and Bassler (1933) and Greacen (1941). The deposits at the type locality, and the Medford site, expose the semi-indurated limesand

faces where “the concentration of bryozoan fragments (especially *Coscinopleura digitata*) reaches its greatest abundance” (Gallagher 1993). The identified taxa found associated are listed in **Table 1**. The abundant foraminifera from the site have not thus far been identified with the exception of *Textularia* sp.

TAXA	CATALOG NUMBER
Foraminifera <i>Textularia</i> sp.	NJSM 24820
Foraminifera <i>Textularia</i> sp.	NJSM 24820
Cnidaria <i>Flabellum mortoni</i> Vaughn	NJSM 24821
Annelida <i>Rotularia rotula</i> (Morton)	NJSM 24825
Annelida <i>Rotularia rotula</i> (Morton)	NJSM 24825
Bryozoa <i>Coscinopleura digitata</i> (Morton) <i>Diacanthopora abbotti</i> (Gabb and Horn)	NJSM 24822 Not assigned
Echinoidea <i>Salenia tumidula</i> Clark <i>Hemiaster unguolata</i> (Morton)	NJSM 24826 NJSM 24827
Bivalvia <i>Polorthis tibialis</i> (Morton) <i>Pycnodonte dissimilaris</i> (Weller) <i>?Cucullaea macrodonta</i> (Whitfield)	NJSM 24823 NJSM 24824 Not assigned
Chondrichthyes <i>Pachygalea lefevrei</i> (Daimeries) <i>Striatolamia striata</i> (Winkler) Odontaspidae indet.	NJSM 24828 NJSM 24829 NJSM 24830

TABLE 1 - Faunal elements associated with NJSM 24294

CONCLUSIONS

The fossil mandible and associated skeletal elements of NJSM 24294 indicate the presence of a very large longirostrine crocodylian during the late Paleocene along the eastern coast of North America. Phylogenetic analysis and the age of this specimen, and additional remains from similarly aged sediments of Maryland and Virginia, indicate that the taxonomic affinity of these large crocodylians cannot be included in either *Thoracosaurus neocesariensis* or *Eosuchus minor* and it is suggested that they should be placed instead in the taxa '*Crocodylus*' *clavirostris*. Additional work, including histological studies, to help provide additional evidence that '*C.*' *clavirostris* is a unique species is in process and it is anticipated that the species will get a new generic name. We also anticipate further analysis of the associated macro and micro invertebrate fauna from the discovery site with the goal of discerning variations of paleoenvironments within the deposition of the Vincentown Formation

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Anthony Lawrence for his discovery and the Medford Mill Homeowners Association for permission to collect and for donation of the specimens. Former Assistant Curator Jason Schein, and Registrar Rodrigo Pellegrini assisted with all aspects of the work, including identification of specimens. Professor Roger Cuffey (Pennsylvania State University) assisted with identification and interpretation of bryozoans. Laura Rooney and Brittany Malinowski assisted in the field, and Susan Parriss assisted with production of the manuscript. Additional support was provided by the New Jersey State Museum Foundation. The New Jersey Conservation Foundation generously permitted prospecting and study of adjacent tracts that are owned by the Foundation. We have also benefited from discussions with Edward Daeschler, William Gallagher, Donald Morgan, Lance Schnatterly, and Robert Weems.

REFERENCES

- Brochu, C.A., 2006. Osteology and phylogenetic significance of *Eosuchus minor* (Marsh 1870), new combination, a longirostrine crocodylian from the Late Paleocene of North America. *J. Paleo.* 80, 162–186
- Canu, F. and Bassler, R. S. 1933. The bryozoan fauna of the Vincentown Limesand. United States National Museum Bulletin 165. 108 pages. 21 plates.
- Carpenter, K. 1983. *Thoracosaurus neocesariensis* (De Kay, 1842) (Crocodylia: Crocodylidae) from the Late Cretaceous Ripley Formation of Mississippi. *Mississippi Geology*, 4(1):1-10.
- de Kay, J. E. 1842. *Zoology of New York*. White & Visscher, New York, 415 p.
- Gallagher, W. B. 1984. Paleocology of the Delaware Valley Region, Part II: Cretaceous to Quaternary. *The Mosasaur*, 2:9-43.
- Gallagher, W. B. 1993. The Cretaceous/Tertiary mass extinction event in the northern Atlantic Coastal Plain. *The Mosasaur*, 5:75–154.
- Gmelin, J. 1789. *Linnei Systema Naturae*. G. E. Beer, Leipzig, 1057 p.
- Greacen, K. F, 1941. The stratigraphy, fauna, and correlation of the Vincentown Formation. Department of Conservation and Development, State of New Jersey Bulletin 52 Geologic Series. 83 pages and Map.
- Hay, O. P. 1930. Second bibliography and catalogue of the fossil Vertebrata of North America. Vol. 2. Carnegie Institute of Washington Publication, 390:1–1074.
- Huxley, T. H. 1875. On *Stagonolepis robertsoni*, and on the evolution of the Crocodylia. *quarterly Journal of the Geological Society*, 31:423–438.

- Marsh, O. C. 1870. Notice of a new species of gavial, from the Eocene of New Jersey. *American Journal of Science*, 50:2–3.
- Morgan, D. J., Weems, R. E., and Parris, D. C. 2018. A new large gavialoid from the Late Paleocene of the eastern United States. Abstract of Poster Paper presented at Society of Vertebrate Paleontology Annual Meeting, Albuquerque, NM.
- Morton, S. G. 1844. Description of the head of a fossil crocodile from the Cretaceous strata of New Jersey. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia*, 2:82–85.
- Sadowski, H. J, Lawrence, A. L., Callahan, W. R., Shankle, W. J., and Conti, L. G. 2017. *Thoracosaurus* (Reptilia: Crocodylidae) in the Vincentown Formation (Paleocene) of New Jersey, U.S.A. Abstract of Poster Paper presented at Joint 52nd Northeastern Section/51st North-Central Section Meeting, Geological Society of America.

Editorial Policy for THE MOSASAUR

The Delaware Valley Paleontological Society was founded in 1978 as an association of amateur and professional paleontologists. The purpose of the Society, as state in its constitution, is "... to promote the gathering and dissemination of information related to fossil forms". THE MOSASAUR is the scientific journal of the Society, and its goals are to further the purposes of the Society and to serve the members of the Society and the general paleontological community. To advance these goals, THE MOSASAUR publishes articles that meet two criteria:

1. Articles must be contributions to paleontology knowledge.
2. Articles must be of interest both to amateur and professional members of the paleontological community.

While there are many paleontological journals currently being published, almost all of them are directed to the Professional and many are quite narrow in scope. Because of the specialized and academic approach of these journals, there are certain types of information that have no easy outlet for publication. These include paleobiogeographic data, locality descriptions, collecting and preparation techniques, and the history of paleontology. The types of articles that the editors of THE MOSASAUR do not seek are descriptions of new species, quantitative analyses, theoretical discussion, travelogues, or generalized reviews of taxonomic groups. There are other, more appropriate outlets for such material. Because of the types of articles that are published and the audience to which they are directed, THE MOSASAUR has its own unique niche among paleontological journals.

Articles for THE MOSASAUR are accepted both from avocational and professional paleontologists. While each article is judged on its own scientific merit, articles should stress original data or compilations of data. Articles submitted by professional paleontologists will be sent to outside referees. Articles submitted by amateur paleontologists will be evaluated by internal referees. The decision as to which category an article falls into will be the responsibility of the editor. Authors submitting manuscripts should submit them as electronic Microsoft Office Word documents which all plates, line drawings, tables and graphs included within the document. For style, writers should follow the general format used in THE MOSASAUR. Citations of all references, including journal names, must be spelled out in full.

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